

TOURISM & HOSPITALITY MARKET DATABASE: GATHERING & UPDATING THE INFORMATION.

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Juraeva Shahzoda Shavkatovna

BSU & UG (university of Gunadarma)
Faculty of Digital Tourism

Abstract: Purpose: Understanding visitor appearance designs is significant for choice creators in arrange to make smart tourism industry. In this article, we display a modern approach based on a market basket analysis. This approach uses questioners and answers data shared by tourists in order to bundle the range of available tourism services and understand which experiences are consumed together. The approach was tested on the case of Bukhara, Uzbekistan. Based on our examinations, we contend that the proposed approach has the potential for utilize at the goal level and gives relevant data on tourism request designs critical for smart tourism decision-making.

Methodology: The field of tourism has developed rapidly in recent years and is becoming one of the main drivers of the economy of our region. The main reason for this is not only the cancellation of visas, the opening of the conversion of our national sum, the granting of customs, tax and credit benefits for representatives of the industry, but also the adoption of necessary decisions that saved the industry from the inevitable crisis during the pandemic. These benefits created the basis for significant work in the field of tourism in the region.

Findings: To get an accurate database of tourism field, we decided to find out the reason of visiting tourists and the most visited tourist destination of Bukhara. In addition we held questionnaires to obtain data mining.

Keywords: market basket analyses, data mining, tourism development, problems and prospects.

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Introduction

Exploring traveler versatility, counting trips to urban tourism goals, is of broad interest in tourism administration [1]. A few variables have contributed to the development of urban tourism: Changing work/leisure designs, such as traveling on long ends of the week, has driven to more visit brief occasions; there is an in general advancement in portability; low-fare tickets have gotten to be accessible; and there's a unavoidable desire for unused encounters [2]. Various endeavors have been made to degree the competitiveness of cities, regions or nations as visitor goals and distinguish the components that contribute to their upgraded and sustained competitive positions [3]. Traveler development inside a goal is frequently respected as a black box that characterizes the behavior of an individual traveler instead of an angle that ought to be explored and clarified [4]. In any case, the developments of travelers inside expansive tourism regions are imperative to understand since they play a crucial part in destination

Uzbekistan has long been considered a country with great tourist potential. The resources of educational tourism are very large. The country has about 7,000

historical and cultural monuments, medieval mosques and madrasas, grandiose architecture of the Tamerlane era. Uzbekistan impresses with its mountain landscape, desert and lakes! The nature of Uzbekistan surprises with incomparable landscapes and gives room for the formation of various options for active tours. The main tourist cities of the country are Bukhara, Samarkand, Khiva, and Tashkent, known since the time of the Great Silk Road (Kamalova S., 2019). Currently, inbound tourism in Uzbekistan is going through difficult times, primarily due to the recent pandemic situation. Recently, the main direction of state support has been the development of inbound and domestic tourism. Although recently there have been positive developments in the development of domestic tourism and attracting foreign visitors (Mirziyoyev, S., 2018).

Methodology.

In tourism studies, the movement of travelers between destinations and their spatial relationship in a large area can be complex [5]. Several previous studies in transport and travel sciences have extracted information from massive trajectory databases, and they have tended to use sequential pattern mining. Alternative data mining methods include association rule mining analysis [6–8], which is a rule-based machine learning method. It has been used to identify groups of variables that are highly correlated with each other from an extensive database or determine patterns of relations between variables of interest. Besides ARM, market basket analysis [9] has been widely used in retail Sustainability 2019, 11, 3967 4 of 17 businesses and marketing research for many decades, and it allows retailers to identify relationships between purchased items and buyer behavior. The most popular algorithm is Apriori, which has been used to extract the frequency of item sets from massive databases and determine association rules to obtain the desired information [10, 11]. This type of analysis works by looking for items that frequently occur together in transactions.

Result.

We were intended to discover firstly bundle of tourist destination in Bukhara, besides agenda of visiting to Bukhara with the assistance of market basket analysis. In order to get dependable results we held two days' questionnaire with a wide range of tourists who are not only foreigners, but also local ones. Participants were from all over the world such as Bulgaria, Italy, France, Kazan, Russia, Belgium, Bangladesh, Pakistan, Yemen, UK, USA, Tajikistan, Kazakhstan and local tourists. According to our studies, we have discovered that the most

visited place in Bukhara was Minaret Kalyan, which is situated in old part of the

#	Name of the country	Aim of visiting		
		Entertainment	Pilgrimage	Study
1	Bulgaria	+		
2	Italy	+		
3	France	+		
4	Kazan	+		
5	Russia	+		
6	Belgium	+		
7	Bangladesh	+	+	
8	USA	+		
9	UK		+	
10	Pakistan		+	
11	Yemen		+	+
12	Tajikistan	+	+	+
13	Kazakhstan	+	+	+
14	Local tourists	+	+	+

city.

The number of hotels in our region in 2017-2022 increased by 4 times, the number of tourist restaurants, guides, tour operators increased by 4.5 times, the number of visiting tourists increased by 5 times, and the number of tourist buses and minibuses increased by 10 times.

As a result of the implementation of decrees and decisions and the conducted propaganda, the number of tourists who came to Bukhara in 2021 was 2 million 265 thousand, and in the eight months of 2022 this figure exceeded 2 million 313 thousand.

The number of local tourists - 2 million 216.5 thousand in 2021, 2 million 12.3 thousand in eight months of 2022;

The number of foreign tourists was 49,000 in 2021, and increased to 363,000 in eight months of 2022.

Employment of means of placement in the region in 2021 was 32.6%, in September 2022, this indicator shows that it has exceeded up to 90%.

Analysis of our surveys among tourists shows that 1 out of 7 of them expressed a desire to return to Uzbekistan again.

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